

THE FILIPINO SISYPHUS: AN ALLEGORY ON THE EXISTENTIAL CONDITION OF POVERTY AND FILIPINO RESILIENCY AN INVESTIGATION ON ALBERT CAMUS' ABSURDITY

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ABSTRACT

This research study explores the profound impact of poverty on Filipino society and individuals, delving into the existential crisis that arises from being trapped in a never-ending cycle of poverty. By examining Albert Camus' concept of absurdity, this study aims to shed light on the struggles of those experiencing poverty and their persistent efforts to find meaning and purpose in a seemingly meaningless existence. Using Camus' absurdist philosophy as a framework, this research paper explores the parallelism between the myth of Sisyphus and the experiences of impoverished Filipinos. The relentless struggle for survival mirrors Sisyphus' endless task of rolling a boulder uphill, yet Filipinos demonstrate remarkable resilience, embodying their defiance against the absurd. This research study through descriptive analysis of cultural narratives, personal accounts, and socio-economic data aims to; understand how the existential implications of poverty affect the totality of the human person, beyond traditional economic definitions. By investigating Camus' philosophical project on absurdity, the study offers new perspectives on the relationship between poverty, existential crises, and the enduring spirit of resilience among Filipinos.

Keywords: *Absurdity, existentialism, existential crisis, poverty, resilience,*

INTRODUCTION

This research study explores the profound impact of poverty on Filipino society and individuals, delving into the existential crisis that arises when individuals are trapped

in a never-ending cycle of poverty. By examining Albert Camus' concept of absurdity, this study seeks to illuminate the struggles of people experiencing poverty and their persistent efforts to find meaning and purpose in a seemingly meaningless existence. By investigating the existential implications of poverty, this research study aspires to a deeper understanding of poverty's challenges that go beyond the traditional economic definition, viewing it as a phenomenon that affects the totality of the human person.

Existentialism is a philosophical movement that emphasizes individual freedom, choice, and responsibility. It focuses on the individual's subjective experience and the search for meaning and purpose in life (White, 2023). Poverty, as an existential crisis, profoundly impacts individuals by depriving them of basic needs and necessary opportunities for meaningful living. When individuals struggle to meet these basic needs, it becomes challenging to pursue dreams or find purpose. According to Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs, physiological needs form the foundational level, including air, water, food, shelter, sleep, and other necessities. The need for self-actualization arises only after these basic needs are met (Maslow, 1943).

Jean-Paul Sartre, a key figure in existentialism, emphasized the importance of human freedom and the responsibility of individuals to define their essence through their choices and actions. His seminal work, "Being and Nothingness," explores existentialist principles, shedding light on human existence, freedom, responsibility, and the individual's confrontation with life's absurdity. Sartre's philosophy indirectly raises questions about the influence of external factors, such as poverty, on human existence (Sartre, 2003).

Albert Camus, another significant existentialist figure, is known for his contributions to absurdism. His works, including "The Stranger," "The Myth of Sisyphus," and "The Stranger," explore themes of the human condition, meaninglessness, and the search for purpose in an indifferent universe. In "The Myth of Sisyphus," Camus examines the existential dilemma of the human desire for meaning in a seemingly indifferent universe. Despite acknowledging the futility of this search, Camus suggests embracing life's absurdity and finding value in the act of rebellion against it.

An existential crisis arises when an individual questions the meaning and purpose of their existence, often accompanied by despair and anxiety (Foley, 2008). For Camus, this crisis emerges from the realization that life has no inherent meaning or purpose: "The absurd is born out of this confrontation between the human need and the unreasonable silence of the world" (Camus, 1942). Poverty can trigger such an existential crisis, leading to a sense of meaninglessness and despair as individuals struggle to meet basic needs. Sartre (1943) argues that poverty can reduce existence to mere survival, causing anxiety and despair. Similarly, in the study of Kruks, (1987) "Simone de Beauvoir and the Limits of Freedom," contends that poverty restricts freedom and limits the ability to create meaning, leading to a sense of powerlessness.

Globally, an estimated 9.2% of the population lived in extreme poverty on less than \$1.90 per day in 2020 World Bank, (2021). In the Philippines, the poverty incidence in 2020 was 21.1%, affecting around 23.5 million people, with significant regional variations Philippine Statistics Authority, (2021). Understanding poverty as an existential crisis involves recognizing it as a condition that profoundly affects individuals' existence, prohibiting authentic living.

Filipino resiliency, defined as the ability to adapt to and recover from difficult situations through social support systems, cultural values, and faith, plays a crucial role in coping with the existential crisis of poverty (Abella and De Guzman, 2017). However, this resilience can be ambivalent. While it is a positive trait, it can also be romanticized, masking the real issues surrounding poverty and perpetuating a culture of acceptance and resignation (Lasco, 2018).

By exploring these themes, this research aims to offer new perspectives on the relationship between poverty, existential crises, and the enduring spirit of resilience among Filipinos, providing valuable insights into the human condition and its manifestations in a specific cultural context.

Research Questions

Main Problem

This research study endeavors to redefine the concept of Filipino resiliency, analyzing its conventional understanding, investigating the impact of romanticization and ambivalence, and proposing a new perspective that sees resilience as a form of metaphysical revolt.

By adopting Camus' absurdist philosophy as a framework, this study seeks to answer the following;

1. What is Albert Camus' notion of absurdity and his proposed response to it?
2. Why poverty is an existential condition of human existence?
3. What is the proper response to poverty's existential condition, and how can it redefine the meaning of Filipino resiliency?

METHODOLOGY

This research study will employ existential investigation and descriptive analysis as its methodology.

Existentialism is a philosophical movement that emphasizes individual freedom, choice, and responsibility, focusing on personal subjective experiences and the search for meaning in life. It explores fundamental questions about human existence, such as its

meaning, purpose, and value, with key concepts including existential crisis, despair, and anxiety (Macquarrie, 1973).

Existential investigation, rooted in this tradition, aims to understand these aspects of human existence through individuals' subjective experiences (Guntman & Pincus, 2003). This research study applies Albert Camus' existentialist absurdist philosophy to understand the existential condition of poverty and Filipino resiliency. It critically analyzes Camus' major works—*The Myth of Sisyphus*, *The Stranger*, and *The Rebel: An Essay on Man in Revolt*—and adopts his notion of "The Metaphysical Revolt" as the appropriate human response to absurdity and poverty. This approach ultimately seeks to redefine the essence of Filipino resiliency.

Descriptive Analysis deals with describing a phenomenon and how we think something is. It attempts to examine the situations to explain the norm. (Baha, 2016). Descriptive analysis as a research method involves gathering data using various methods. In this research study, the primary method of collecting data is through content analysis and careful scrutinization and explanation of the existing records, documents, and literature related to the subject. The data gathered are presented by summarizing the key themes, patterns, and narratives that emerge in the data collected. Though descriptive analysis as a research method is commonly used in quantitative research, the researcher believes that it can be applied in qualitative research design through careful and thoughtful description and analysis of the phenomenon being investigated through textual analysis.

Scope and Delimitation

This research study delves into Albert Camus' absurdist philosophy, connecting it with the existential challenges of poverty and the resilience of Filipinos. The study involves a meticulous review of pertinent literature and a comprehensive analysis of relevant primary and secondary references. It is important to note that the scope of this study is limited to the Filipino context, and the findings may not broadly apply to other cultural or societal settings. The research adopts a qualitative approach, drawing insights from scholarly literature and academic journals. Notably, this qualitative methodology refrains from direct engagement with participants through surveys, interviews, or focus groups, relying instead on the wealth of existing knowledge and expert analyses available in the academic realm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Camus Notion of Absurdity and His Proposed Response to It

Albert Camus' notion of absurdity revolves around the idea that life is inherently devoid of meaning or purpose because of the fundamental tension between the human desire for meaning and the indifference of the universe. Absurdity is an ontological reality of human existence that individuals must confront. "At this point of his effort, a man stands face to face with the irrational. He feels within him his longing for happiness and reason. The absurd is born of this confrontation between the human need and the unreasonable silence of the world." (Camus, *The Myth of Sisyphus*, 1942). Responding to the problem

of absurdity, Camus proposes the concept of “revolt,” which involves a conscious and active engagement with life’s inherent absurdity, embracing freedom and authenticity, rejection of despair and nihilism and the quest for illusory meaning.

The Conflict Between Human Desire and the Universe

At this point of his effort, a man stands face to face with the irrational. He feels within him his longing for happiness and reason. The absurd is born of this confrontation between human needs and the unreasonable silence of the world (Camus, 1942, MS: 25; E: 173).

Desire is a fundamental aspect of human nature that encompasses human needs, wants, cravings, and aspirations. It is an inclination or longing for something perceived as lacking and, once fulfilled, becomes a source of fulfillment (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2009). From the perspective of existentialism, desire is the emphasis on human freedom. The emphasis on freedom could be seen in the works of prominent existentialists like Sartre, Camus, and Nietzsche. In “Being and Nothingness,” Sartre (1943) famously stated, “Man is condemned to be free,” understanding this statement means that humans are free to choose their actions without any interference, but freedom, however, comes with the burden of responsibility. Camus’ understanding of desire stems from humans’ innate longing for reason and understanding. “At this point of his effort, a man stands face to face with the irrational. He feels within him his longing for happiness and reason. p.25” (Camus, *The Myth of Sisyphus*, 1942). According to Camus, the origin of the absurd was from the conflict of man not being able to rationalize and explain his existence in human terms. He holds that reality poses a peculiar problem for humans, whose rationality cannot help searching, looking, struggling, and critically looking at life. So, he said, “... that odd state of the sour in which the chain of daily gestures is broken, in which the heart vainly seeks the link that will connect it again, it is, as it were, the first sign of absurdity” (Arinze & Onwuatuegwu, 2020).

Camus’ philosophy pictured the universe as indifferent to the needs and desires of humans, though meaningful on its own; for humans, its utter meaninglessness poses a significant threat to human existence. One real-life illustration of this absurdity can be seen in the face of natural disasters. Consider a devastating earthquake that struck a populated city. In an instant, lives are lost, families are shattered, properties are destroyed, and homes are reduced to rubble. The earthquake itself is indifferent to human needs and the suffering it causes. An earthquake has no inherent meaning; it is a force of nature that cannot be avoided. The least humans can do is blindly anticipate that it may happen at any time. In the aftermath of such a catastrophe, humans grapple with the profound silence of the universe and ask why such a catastrophe occurred, seeking meaning or reason behind man’s suffering. However, the universe remains silent, offering no explanations or justification for the pain and loss of man.

Humans desire to make the world intelligible; however, reality strikes that no matter how hard humans try, there are questions that cannot be answered and events that cannot be explained. The human being is divorced from his dwelling place.

The Problem of Suicide

There is but one truly serious philosophical problem and that is suicide. Judging whether life is or is not worth living amounts to answering the fundamental question of philosophy. All the rest— whether or not the world has three dimensions, whether the mind has nine or twelve categories—comes afterward. (Camus, 1942, *The Myth of Sisyphus*, p. 84)

Questioning the value and meaning of human existence is the core of philosophical inquiry. With the discovery of the absurd, two alternatives are open to the man “who lives based on what he knows” and “does not cheat.” Man must choose suicide or recovery. The question is, can man find life absurd and still go on living (Caraway, 1992).

In the *Myth of Sisyphus*, Camus elaborated on two forms of suicide: physical and philosophical. Physical suicide is the act of intentionally ending one's life. It is a direct response to the perceived absurdity of existence. Individuals contemplating physical suicide often do so because they cannot find meaning or purpose in life, and ending their lives seems like the only way to escape the existential pain and despair. Camus does not advocate for physical suicide; instead, he encourages individuals to confront the absurdity of life and find a reason to live despite its inherent meaninglessness.

Philosophical suicide, according to Camus, is a subtler form of suicide. It occurs when someone embraces religious or ideological beliefs that provide comforting, absolute meanings or explanations for existence. In this case, individuals “philosophically” commit suicide by escaping the absurd through faith or dogma. “The leap in all its forms, rushing into the divine or the eternal, surrendering to the illusion of the everyday or of the idea - all these screens and hide the absurd” (Camus, 1942, MS p. 35). By accepting a ready-made belief system that promises an ultimate purpose or an afterlife, people avoid confrontation with the inherent meaninglessness of life. Camus criticizes this form of suicide because it involves a deliberate intellectual evasion of the absurd, replacing it with false certainties. Caraway, (2002) suggests that, while the existential philosophers have realized the absurdity that links man and the world, according to Camus, “all of them without exception suggest escape.” For example, Jaspers and Chestov (*Myth of Sisyphus*, 24, 25), realizing nothing in experience to infer any satisfactory principle that would negate the absurd and man's impotence, posit God as the only true solution. Camus’ response to any attempt to go beyond human experience and reason is unequivocal; in the *Myth of Sisyphus*, he wrote:

“I don't know whether this world has a meaning that transcends it. But I know that I do not know = that meaning and that it is impossible for me just now to know it. What can a meaning outside my condition mean to me? I can understand only in human terms” (Camus, 1942).

The Absurd Heroes

In Albert Camus' philosophy, the "absurd hero" is exemplified by Sisyphus, a figure from Greek mythology condemned to eternally push a boulder up a mountain only to have it roll back down each time he reaches the summit. Camus uses Sisyphus to illustrate the human condition, marked by a perpetual search for meaning in an indifferent universe. Despite the futility of his task, Sisyphus continues with determination, embodying the essence of the absurd hero. By accepting the absurdity of his situation and finding contentment in the struggle itself, Sisyphus achieves a form of freedom and defiance, demonstrating that meaning and happiness can be found in the act of perseverance itself.

Two of the Absurd heroes in Camus' absurdist philosophy are Sisyphus and Meursault. These absurd heroes show different responses to the Absurd: The former is through active defiance and perseverance, and the latter is through passive acceptance and authenticity. Both characters exemplify Absurd heroism by confronting the meaninglessness of existence in their ways, reflecting Camus' exploration of the diverse human responses to the Absurdity of the human condition. By presenting these two contrasting characters, Camus provides a distinct understanding of the Absurd and how individuals navigate their existence in an indifferent universe.

While Sisyphus's victory is profound on an individual level, it does not extend to the collective or historical sphere. As Camus describes, the Absurd is an inherent conflict between human beings' search for meaning and the indifferent, chaotic universe. Sisyphus's victory does not alter the universe's nature or the human condition's absurdity for others. It remains a personal triumph, applicable to his own experience, but not something that fundamentally transforms the more significant human struggle with the Absurd.

Meursault, the protagonist of Camus' novel "The Stranger," embodies the Absurd Hero differently. Meursault is detached and indifferent to the world around him. He shows little emotion, even in the face of significant events such as his mother's death or his trial. He accepts the universe's indifference and lives according to his desires and impulses.

Meursault's rebellion against the Absurd is rooted in his refusal to conform to societal expectations. He did not grieve at his mother's funeral and did not show remorse during his trial. Instead, he embraces his nature, living authentically without the constraints of social norms and moral judgments. This nonconformity grants him a sense of freedom, even though it leads to tragic consequences. His indifference, acceptance of the Absurd, and genuine authenticity make him a symbol of the Absurd Hero. Meursault's story challenges traditional concepts of morality and meaning, illustrating the complexities of human existence in a universe devoid of inherent purpose.

Sisyphus and Meursault differ in their attitudes and responses to the Absurd. Sisyphus finds meaning in the act of defiance, in the repetitive task itself. His rebellion is active and continuous. On the other hand, Meursault rebels by embracing his nature and living authentically. His rebellion is passive, a refusal to conform to the expectations and norms imposed by society. Though they differ in their attitude and response to the absurd, Sisyphus and Meursault display courage in confronting the absurd. This courage lies in

their conscious choice to live authentically by recognizing the meaninglessness of human existence and constantly and actively rejecting it through revolt.

The Rebel an Essay on Man in Revolt: A Philosophical Response to the Absurd

“What is a rebel? A man who says no, but whose refusal does not imply a renunciation. He is also a man who says yes, from the moment he makes his first gesture of rebellion. . . . Rebellion cannot exist without the feeling that, somewhere and somehow, one is right. It is in this way that the rebel slave says yes and no simultaneously” (Camus, 1956).

Camus’ depiction of the rebel is someone who says “no” and simultaneously says “yes” in the face of the inherent meaninglessness of human existence. The “yes” signifies the acceptance of the reality of the absurd, and the “no” signifies the active rejection and repulsion that life amidst the reality of absurdity is devoid of meaning. The reality of the absurd did not negate human existence and meaning but affirmed it! The absurdity arising from man’s irrational relationship to the universe negated not the meaning of human existence but the meaning attributed to it. The dialectical encapsulates the human condition. It reflects the constant struggle and negotiation between affirming life and rejecting its absurd aspects. This tension embodies the complexity of human existence, where individuals navigate between finding meaning and confronting meaninglessness. It illustrates the ongoing battle between hope and despair, creation and destruction, affirmation and negation. This dialectical response underscores the richness and depth of human experience, acknowledging the coexistence of moments of joy, love, and purpose with moments of suffering, absurdity, and despair (Caraway, 1992).

In contrast to the traditional understanding of a “rebel” as someone who openly opposes, resists, and defies authority as well as social norms and established beliefs, the “rebel” as portrayed by Camus is someone who engages in philosophical contemplation, questioning the fundamental aspects of existence while exploring the meaning of life given the existential condition of the human person. The rebel’s rebellion is rooted not in violence but in recognizing the absurd as a fundamental aspect of human existence and condition and courageously resisting it. Its rebellion is a courageous act against the inherent meaninglessness of life, refusing to succumb to despair and nihilism. Further, the rebel values autonomy and freedom by rejecting imposed societal norms, dogmas, and ideologies, blatantly asserting independence in thought and action, making the act of rebellion not influenced by external influences but something that arises from one’s convictions and reasoning. The Rebel understands that life lacks inherent meaning yet engages in creative endeavors and meaningful actions because its rebellion involves the discovery of personal meaning and significance in a universe devoid of meaning. This is possible due to the freedom discovered in the realization and dialectic response to the absurd.

“The rebel, then, is the absurd man.” The absurd man, the rebel, lives only based on personal experience. It does not scorn reason. Instead, it uses reason but admits the irrational. He is little inclined to leap before knowing. “He sees no further place for hope beyond this life. However, most importantly, he sees that only this life has value. He rebels against death and for life” (Caraway, 1992). The rebel does not conform to the norms of

the society or any form of ideologies, acknowledges the irrational aspects of human existence, and uses reason to understand the world while simultaneously recognizing its limitations, but chooses not to succumb to take the “leap.” The rebel embraces the irrational, signifying acceptance of human existence's inexplicable reality. The “no” to the absurdity and the “yes” to life highlights the rebel's clinging and love for being and existing. For this reason, Sisyphus's condemnation of the absurd task, contrary to the belief of the gods as the greatest punishment, is Sisyphus's greatest reward to live among the gods and be eternal like them. The rebel's love for being and existing amidst the absurdity of his existence makes the rebel the “absurd man. An examination of man's relation to the world reveals that the only knowledge that man has is that he now has his present life, but that he is, to use Heidegger's phrase "a being-to ward-death." Thus, the only value that man knows is life. The rebel, therefore, rebels against death and for life” (Caraway, 1992).

The human person's external defiance against the absurd and internal philosophical stance distinguished the rebel from the rest. The rebel confronts the absurd with unwavering courage, a creative spirit, and authenticity.

The Metaphysical Revolt

“Revolt is the ongoing struggle with the absurd, a struggle which maintains the tension between man's desires and what the world offers without allowing man to negate either pole by escaping through suicide on the one hand or hope which does not conform to man's experience on the other hand” (Caraway, 1992).

In Albert Camus' philosophy, metaphysical revolt refers to the inherent human resistance against the absurdity of existence. It is a rebellion not against specific injustices or societal oppressions but against the universe's very nature, which Camus characterizes as inherently devoid of meaning or purpose (Hanna, 1958). This existential crisis paved the way for the metaphysical revolt against the fundamental aspect of reality and the human condition that appears devoid of inherent meaning or value. Metaphysical revolt is not the same as political or social rebellion, which results from injustice and oppression experienced by individuals or groups. Metaphysical revolt transcends the notion of rebellion underscored in societal concerns; it is not a rebellion against an unjust government but a rebellion against the universe and its inherent meaninglessness (Caraway, 1992). In the silence of the universe, metaphysical revolt signifies the human person's refusal to accept that life is absurd. It is the resistance and insistence of the human spirit to seek meaning and purpose in an indifferent universe. In the face of a universe that does not offer inherent meaning or values, human beings experience a profound sense of disorientation and absurdity. Metaphysical revolt is the response to this existential crisis. It is a rebellion against the silence of the cosmos, the lack of answers to fundamental questions, and the absence of any ultimate purpose in life (Foley, 2008).

Understanding Poverty as an Existential Condition of Human Existence

Poverty is a significant issue in the Philippines, affecting a large portion of the population. According to the latest data, the poverty incidence among Filipinos in 2020 was 21.1%, or around 23.5 million people (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2021). When existence is consumed by "the daily struggle for survival," the pursuit of authentic and

meaningful existence becomes distant. An existential approach to poverty examines how this deprivation of meaning and purpose affects the overall well-being of an individual. Adopting an existential lens in understanding poverty becomes a profound philosophical inquiry that prompts questions about the human condition, societal values, and the ethical responsibilities of individuals and communities in addressing the issue. It, therefore, unravels the more profound implications of poverty, moving beyond economic terminologies and statistical data. Traditionally, poverty is often perceived in economic terms, and it is a state wherein a person lacks the material resources to survive, such as food, shelter, and clothing. Economic aspects are undeniably crucial in living a happy and authentic existence. However, this perspective reduces the impact of poverty on biological and physical needs. Poverty is not just about an individual's economic capabilities; it is an existential condition of human beings that consequently causes an existential crisis, forcing one to question the meaning attributed to life. When examined through the existential lenses, poverty challenges an individual at a fundamental level, making one question their identity and self-worth. A person's identity and self-worth cannot be reduced to economic capabilities and how much money they possess, but also through their beliefs and aspirations, which give life meaning.

Camus' analysis of the absurdity of the human condition and existence can be extended to understand poverty as an existential condition of man. In this context, poverty exists because of man's irrational relationship with fellow human beings. The struggle for necessities and the social injustices, coupled with the inability of the social structures to respond to people's needs, exemplify the clash between the human desire for dignity, purpose, and meaning. The blatant contradiction between the human desire for meaning and the irrationality of human societal structures and relationships perpetuates the existence of poverty, which stresses the absurdity of the human condition.

An Absurd Human Relationship

According to Aristotle, humans are social beings, thriving in social interactions and forming societies. Conflict naturally arises in societies due to individual uniqueness and differences (Dixon, 2010). To mitigate this, humans enter social contracts. Thomas Hobbes argued in "Leviathan" that without societal structures, life in the "state of nature" would be nasty, brutish, and short, leading to barbarism in resolving conflicts. He posited that individuals willingly surrender some freedom to governing authorities for security and order (Martinich, 2003). John Locke, in his social contract theory, believed individuals enter into social contracts to secure their rights to liberty and property, and if the government fails to protect these rights, the people have the right to overthrow it (Jos, 2006). Societal conventions are established to address conflicts from human interactions, creating a structured environment with shared norms, beliefs, culture, and systems to maintain order and define individual roles, rights, and responsibilities (Martinich, 2003). As rational beings, humans can discern the potential consequences of their actions, knowing what constitutes acceptable behavior in society. Despite this knowledge, individuals may choose to act otherwise. To be considered a "good man" in society, one must often perform actions benefiting others, sometimes at the expense of personal happiness, while doing the opposite may label one as selfish or a "bad person," illustrating that "being good" often requires suspending personal gratification..

Desire, which is inherent in humans, urges man to act. Desire, commonly understood as having a strong feeling of wanting or having something, compels humans to act and satisfy wants and needs; it catalyzes human actions (Anderson, 2015). It implies that wants and needs play a significant role in motivating humans to pursue goals. According to Bertrand Russell in his acceptance speech for the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1950, "All human activity is prompted by desire.

"Some earnest moralist advances a wholly fallacious theory to the effect that it is possible to resist desire in the interest of duty and moral principle. I say this is fallacious, not because no man ever acts from a sense of duty, but because duty has no hold on him unless he desires to be dutiful. If you wish to know what men will do, you must know not only, or principally, their material circumstances, but rather the whole system of their desires with their relative strength" (Russell, 1950).

All human action is driven by desire, and if knowing is the first step in doing, it implies that in the performance of any human act, an individual is capable of knowing if an action will cause harm to others and if acted to do so, it only shows that the satisfaction of desire comes first. It is what causes the conflict in human relationships. Even if an act is performed because of a sense of duty, the satisfaction of desires still comes first. Bertrand Russell labeled this kind of desire as vanity. "Vanity is a motive of immense potency; "look at me" is one of the most fundamental desires of the human heart. It can take innumerable forms, from buffoonery to posthumous fame" (Russell, 1950). This means that the action, because of a sense of duty, is driven by the desire to be known to be famous.

Russell further elaborates in his speech that human desire is insatiable, "but man differs from other animals, that is so to speak man's desire is infinite, which can never be fully gratified and would keep him restless even in paradise. Russell labels four human desires: acquisitiveness, rivalry, vanity, and love of power" (Russell, 1950). Acquisitiveness is the desire to possess as much as possible of goods. Despite having enough to survive, man desires to retain more. Russell briefly recounted his experience of the two little girls whom he saved from starvation in Estonia. The girls in his family have more than enough food to survive, but despite this, "they spent their leisure visiting neighboring farms stealing potatoes which they hoarded." It shows that man will always desire to acquire more, no matter how much he/she possesses.

Rivalry, according to Russell, (1950) is the desire to outdo the others because man's perception of the other is not a comrade but a rival. Economically, man sees others as a rival over scarce resources; for this reason, man, due to acquisitive desire, will do everything to possess the resources.

"But great as is the influence of the motives we have been considering, there is one which outweighs them all. I mean the love of power. Love of power is closely akin to vanity, but it is not the same thing. Vanity needs glory for satisfaction, and it is easy to have glory without power" (Russell, 1950). The desire for power outweighs acquisitiveness, rivalry, and vanity. Vanity desires fame, glory, and recognition; rivalry desires the destruction of the other, and acquisitiveness desires possessions; the love of power desires dominion and control. It drives an individual to pursue positions of authority

and leadership, which grant an individual dominion and power over others. Possessing such power means easy access to resources, destruction of rivals, and fame and glory.

Ideally, human relationships should be characterized by mutual respect, empathy, and compassion, equity and fairness, shared values, and goals. However, as long as human desire exists, such ideal relationships will not exist, and man will continue to harm fellow man in the process of satisfying desire. It is for this reason that human relationships are irrational and absurd. Human reason dictated what human relationships should be, but the very heart of human experience tells otherwise. Human relationships are absurd!

Poverty as a Condition of Human Existence

Applying Albert Camus' framework of absurdity to understand poverty as an existential condition involves recognizing the tension between the human desire for a meaningful existence and societal relationships. Humans seek peaceful coexistence but are driven by insatiable desires, which often lead to conflict. Bertrand Russell noted that humans, unlike animals, have infinite desires that can never be fully satisfied, causing restlessness even in ideal conditions (Russell, 1950). This insatiability leads to indifference toward others' needs.

Ideally, societal conventions should guide actions toward justice and harmony. However, individual autonomy allows people to transcend these norms and pursue their desires, often at the expense of others. In the context of poverty, societal norms suggest that excessive wealth leads to greed and inequality. Although reason should temper human desire, it often supports systems like capitalism that protect individual wealth and control resources, exacerbating poverty (Smith, 2002). Capitalism fuels the human drive for possessions and power, making individuals blind to others' needs.

This tension between desire and relationships suggests that poverty is a condition of human existence. It persists not due to actual scarcity but to justify acquisitive desires. Humanity has the resources to eradicate poverty; what is needed is the equitable distribution of these resources to allow everyone opportunities for self-realization rather than mere subsistence. Karl Marx proposed communism as a solution, advocating for the equal distribution of resources, which he believed required a revolution to achieve (Raekstad, 2018).

The Resilience of the Filipino Sisyphus

This study establishes that poverty is an existential condition resulting from the tension between the human desire for meaning and the irrationality of human relationships. The Filipino absurd hero, in the context of poverty, acknowledges this condition but revolts against it through resilience, a unique Filipino trait. Resiliency is Filipinos' act of defiance against poverty's absurdity, allowing them to find meaning despite challenges.

According to the Philippine Statistic Association (PSA), 16.7% of Filipinos lived below the poverty line in 2021, with fisherfolk, farmers, and rural residents most affected (Philippine Statistic Authority, 2021). A 2023 Social Weather Station survey revealed that 51% of Filipino families consider themselves poor (CNN, 2023). The World Bank's global poverty threshold is \$2.15 daily, while the PSA sets it at P80.02, criticized for being too

low (Dela Peña, 2023). Poverty impacts various life aspects, including healthcare, education, employment, and overall well-being (Adler & Newman, 2002; Duncan, 2010; World Bank, 2019).

Studies show that poverty also brings social stigmas, associating the poor with criminality, dirtiness, and laziness (Rosales, 2013; Bernardo, 2013). Media often romanticizes poverty, portraying it as noble, which can lead to exploitation and marginalization (Ehrenreich, 2001). Filipinos' coping mechanisms, such as reliance on faith and communal support (Bayanihan), highlight their resilience (Rilveria, 2018).

Resilience, defined by the American Psychological Association as the ability to bounce back from adversity, is deeply rooted in Filipino cultural values and social support systems. This includes family bonds and community solidarity (Umbal & Salanga, 2018). Filipino resilience is also characterized by positivity and humor, which help navigate difficult situations (Salazar, 2010).

However, reliance on faith and religiosity can be seen as evasion of the existential condition, which Camus termed "philosophical suicide" (Foley, 2008). Yet, this study acknowledges that faith and religiosity provide Filipinos with strength and endurance, a departure from Camus' strict rejection of transcendental meaning.

This research diverges from Camus by recognizing the unique cultural context of Filipino resilience, which combines existential awareness with faith. While Camus emphasized confronting the absurd without external frameworks, this study argues that, for Filipinos, faith is a vital source of strength.

On the other hand, redefining Filipino resilience within Camus' framework encourages a self-reliant approach, emphasizing human agency and rationality. This perspective suggests that true resilience can emerge without divine assurance, encouraging critical thinking and empirical reasoning (Garnham, 1967; Foley, 2008).

Ultimately, Filipino resilience is diverse, drawing strength from both existential awareness and faith. This study promotes an inclusive perspective, recognizing that individuals can find strength and meaning in various ways when confronting existential challenges. This approach respects individual choices and cultural backgrounds, fostering collective resilience grounded in Filipino existential experiences.

Metaphysical Revolt, Towards Authentic Resilience

Metaphysical rebellion, as described by Camus, is the act of defiance against the inherent condition of human existence and the universe's lack of meaning. This form of rebellion is not against societal injustices but against the absurdity of life itself (Camus, 1956). Camus acknowledges life's absurdity but rejects nihilism and religious transcendence as responses. Instead, he proposes metaphysical revolt, which is a rebellion against the universe's meaninglessness and an assertion of human spirit seeking meaning (Caraway, 1992).

In the context of poverty, metaphysical revolt involves recognizing poverty as a fundamental human condition arising from irrational human relationships. The insatiable

human desire, as noted by Bertrand Russell, drives individuals to indifference and societal conventions often fail to temper this desire, leading to injustice and inequality (Russell, 1950).

The plight of the poor parallels Sisyphus' struggle. Despite their cyclical and seemingly endless struggles against poverty, the poor continue to hope and live, manifesting their reluctance to accept life's meaninglessness. Their daily perseverance against economic challenges and stigmatization is a form of revolt against their absurd condition. This is encapsulated in the Filipino tagline, "Para kanino ka bumabangon?" which highlights living for others, especially family, as a source of meaning (Filipino coffee brand tagline).

Conclusions

Resiliency Redefined

Traditional resilience suggests "bouncing back" to a prior state after adversity, similar to a rubber band returning to its shape. This notion is flawed as it implies reverting to pre-challenge conditions, overlooking the personal growth that should accompany overcoming difficulties. For instance, after natural disasters, affected individuals are expected to rebuild and return to normalcy. This expectation often masks governmental and institutional failures, as resilience becomes an excuse for inaction.

Breaking Point and Transformation

Human resilience, like a rubber band, has a breaking point. Excessive stress can lead to despair and self-destructive behaviors, evidenced by the link between poverty, crime, and substance abuse. Thus, resilience should be seen not merely as recovery but as a transformative process involving reflection, learning, and growth. Individuals should not only survive challenges but also adapt and thrive, gaining strength and insight from adversity.

Bouncing Forward

Patricia Longstaff's concept of "bouncing forward" emphasizes growth and improvement post-adversity. "Bouncing forward" is a concept that emphasizes an individual's or a community's ability not only to bounce back from adversity or difficult circumstances but also to grow and thrive as a result of those challenges. Rather than simply returning to the previous state, resilient individuals and communities undergo a transformative process that enables them to adapt, learn, and improve their situation (Hynes et al., 2020). Resilience involves not just overcoming but harnessing adversity to emerge stronger and wiser. This process requires reflection, adaptability, and the willingness to learn and change. Michaela Haas's book, "Bouncing Forward: Transforming Bad Breaks into Breakthroughs," illustrates how individuals can turn hardships into opportunities for personal growth (Haas, 2015).

Pagpupunyagi

"Pagpupunyagi," a Filipino term, encapsulates the essence of true resilience. It goes beyond mere survival, signifying continuous effort, perseverance, and the quest for meaning despite challenges. It reflects an active pursuit of growth and development, acknowledging the absurdity of life yet finding purpose through persistent effort. *Pagpupunyagi* goes beyond survival, working, and consuming oneself for physical sustenance. It encompasses an active pursuit that will give meaning to existence; despite the challenges an individual may encounter, it signifies their commitment to personal growth and development. The inherent optimism of *pagpupunyagi* acknowledges the absurdity of the human condition, but at the same time, it also embraces the transformative power of such a condition. An individual now has the power to create meaning imposed not by society nor the pre-established meaning offered by religion but a meaning generated through the individual's effort to thrive and find meaning amidst the absurdity.

The Filipino Sisyphus

The Filipino Sisyphus symbolizes the relentless Filipino spirit, striving for meaning amidst the absurdity of poverty and existential challenges. This symbolic figure represents ordinary Filipinos, like workers, street vendors, slum dwellers, and teachers, who persist daily despite daunting circumstances. These individuals embody "pagpupunyagi," accepting and revolting against life's absurdity through their dedication and perseverance.

The Filipino Sisyphus reflects the resilience and determination of Filipinos who, despite acknowledging the absurdity of their condition, persistently strive to find and create meaning in their lives. This relentless pursuit, embodied in "pagpupunyagi," signifies the true essence of resilience, transforming adversity into a source of strength and purpose. Tuloy pa rin ang laban ng buhay!!!

Recommendations

In light of the findings of this research, "The Filipino Sisyphus: An Allegory on the Existential Crisis of Poverty and Filipino Resiliency—an Investigation on Albert Camus' Absurdity," several recommendations emerge to enrich our understanding of Filipino resilience and its intersection with existential philosophy

1. Expand the investigation and improve the findings of this research by delving into other existentialist and nihilist philosophies that can contribute to a much more profound understanding of Filipino resilience.
2. Conduct qualitative studies that delve into the personal narratives of individuals who have experienced poverty, exploring the factors contributing to their resilience.
3. Conduct cross-cultural analyses of resilience in poverty to extend the research beyond the Filipino context.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research study employs a qualitative research design. The study involves a meticulous review of pertinent literature and a comprehensive analysis of relevant primary and secondary references. By rigorously examining existing scholarly works, and articles, the study ensures a clear understanding of the topic under investigation while upholding ethical standards for resource utilization. As such, it refrains from direct engagement with participants through surveys, interviews, or focus groups. This decision aligns with ethical considerations, aiming to respect the autonomy and privacy of individuals while avoiding potential biases or undue influence on the findings of this research. Instead, the study relies solely on the wealth of existing knowledge and resources available to ensure the integrity and validity of its conclusions. Further, there is no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and the results were used purely for research.

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